

R_f VALUES AND THE DISTANCE OF THE STARTING POINT FROM THE SOURCE OF SOLVENT IN FILTER PAPER CHROMATOGRAPHY

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The R_f values of the amino-acids gradually decrease with the increase of the distance of their starting point from the source of solvent. This is attributed to gradual loss of water-content of the solvent during its movement along the paper. Total loss of water has been roughly calculated and it has been shown that the distribution of solvent and water is not uniform throughout.

The solution to be subjected to paper chromatography is applied a few cms. away from the edge of the paper, which dips into the developing solvent. In the two-way chromatography the solution is applied near one of the corners of a sheet of paper and a few cms. away from both the edges, which are to be successively dipped in the developing solvents. It has been observed by Consden *et al.* (*Biochem. J.*, 1944, 38, 224) that the rates of movement of the amino-acids (expressed in terms of R_f values) depend upon this distance between the starting point and the source of solvent. A detailed study of this 'distance' factor has been made in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the study of the distance factor, phenol > water and pyridine-amyl alcohol-water (35 : 35 : 30) have been used in the descending way and isopropyl alcohol-water (7 : 3) in the ascending way.

The descending chromatography was carried out in a cabinet specially made according to the specifications of Dent (*Biochem. J.*, 1948, 43, 169) with slight modifications. The cabinet is made out of Swedish boards, inside dimensions being 80 cm. × 80 cm. × 20 cm. It is provided with glass windows on both the sides and a tight-fitting lid; 10 cms. below the lid there are supports on both the sides for the stainless steel trough and for the sheets of paper held into this trough. The developing solvent is added to the trough through a small opening at the centre of the lid after the filter papers have been allowed to equilibrate within for 8 to 12 hours with the vapours of the developing solvent. The equipment used for the ascending way of development was the same as described in a previous communication (Burma and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 135).

The R_f values of an amino-acid for various distances from the source of solvent were determined on the same sheet of filter paper. For the descending run, a piece of sheet (46.4 cm. \times 56.3 cm.) of Whatman filter No. 1 was used. Point marks by graphite pencil were made on this paper 2 cm. apart from each other but at various distances from the edge of the paper as shown in Fig. 1. The first point was as usual 7.5 cm. away from the edge which was placed in the trough. Other points were marked such that the distances of the consecutive points increased by 2 cm. All the points thus lay on a line at an angle 45° to the edge. 0.0025 ML. of an amino-acid solution was applied at each point. The paper was developed and the positions of the amino-acids on the chromatogram were indicated in the usual way.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

For the ascending run, sheets of smaller size (29 cm \times 30 cm.) were used (Fig. 2). The first point was 1.5 cm. away from the lower edge and the distances of the consecutive points increased by 2 cm. as in the previous case.

Table I records the R_f values of some of the amino-acids applied at uniformly increasing distances, as described above, using the descending way, and phenol-water as the developing solvent. The distance moved by the solvent front in each case is also recorded. The spots of a particular amino-acid are found to lie more or less on a straight line which is, however, not parallel either to the starting line or the solvent front (Fig. 1).

Table II records the R_f values of some of the amino-acids obtained in the similar manner using pyridine-amyl alcohol-water in the descending way and Table III records those of a few amino-acids using isopropyl alcohol-water as the developing solvent in the ascending way. Peculiarly enough, in the latter case the spots fall on two straight lines intersecting at a large

angle. The change of slope, although small, is not negligible (Fig. 2).¹⁰ The break occurs, as can be seen from the figure, near the spot corresponding to the distance of 14 cm. away from the starting point.

TABLE I

Developing solvent : Phenol > water.

(Descending way).

Dist. from the first start- ing point.	Aspartic acid.	Glutamic acid.	Serine.	Glycine.	Alanine.	Valine.	Leucine.	Phenyl- alanine.
	48.8 cm.	49.1 cm	46.5 cm	48. cm.	49.5cm.	48 cm.	47.8 cm	49 cm.
0 cm.	0.21	0.31	0.39	0.44	0.58	0.76	0.85	0.85
2	.21	.30	.39	.43	.59	.76	.85	.86
4	.18	.30	.38	.42	.58	.76	.85	.85
6	.18	.29	.37	.41	.58	.75	.85	.85
8	.17	.28	.38	.41	.59	.75	.83	.85
10	.17	.27	.37	.41	.57	.74	.83	.85
12	.17	.27	.36	.40	.57	.74	.83	.86
14	.16	.26	.36	.40	.57	.74	.82	.85
16	.16	.26	.36	.40	.57	.74	.81	.84
18	.15	.26	.36	.37	.56	.74	.80	.82
20	.14	.26	.35	.39	.57	.75	.80	.84
22	.14	.25	.35	.39	.56	.74	.80	.86
24	.14	.24	.35	.38	.56	.75	.80	.84
26	.13	.23	.34	.37	.55	.73	.81	.83
28	.13	.23	.33	.35	.54	.70	.82	.81
30	.12	.22	.33	.35	.51	.71	.80	.78
32	.12	.21	.32	.35	.50	.67	.80	.77
34	.12	.21	.31	.34	.50	.67	.80	.77
36	.12	.21	.31	.34	.50	.66	.80	.77
38	.11	.20	.31	.33	.49	.66	.79	.77
40	.11	.20	.30	.33	.48	.64	.77	.77
42	.10	.20	.26	.33	.47	.63	.77	.76
44	.08	.19	.25	.32	.47	.61	.75	.76

TABLE II
 Developing solvent : Pyridine-amyl alcohol-water (35:35:30).
 (Descending way).

Dist. from the 1st starting point.	Threonine.	Valine.	isoLeucine.	Phenylalanin.
	Distance moved by the solvent front.			
	39.8 cm.	43 cm.	45 cm.	45 cm.
0 cm.	0.13	0.23	0.35	0.45
2	.12	.21	.34	.43
4	.09	.20	.32	.43
6	.08	.19	.31	.41
8	.08	.19	.31	.38
10	.07	.18	.28	.39
12	.06	.17	.28	.37
14	.06	.17	.27	.36
16	.06	.15	.26	.35
18	.05	.14	.25	.34
20	.05	.13	.26	.33
22	.04	.13	.25	.32
24	.04	.12	.24	.32
26	.04	.11	.22	.30
28	.03	.12	.21	.28
30	.02	.09	.20	.26
32	0.0	.08	.17	.25
34	0.0	.07	.19	.22
36	0.0	.07	.17	.15
38	0.0	0.0	.16	.14
40	-	0.0	.12	0.0
42	-	0.0	0.0	0.0
44	-	-	0.0	0.0

TABLE III

Developing solvent ; *iso*Propyl alcohol : water (7 : 3).

(Ascending way).

Distance from 1st starting point.	Asparagine.	Aspartic acid.	Glutamic acid.	Glycine.	Alanine.	Methionine.	Phenyl- alanine.
	Distance moved by the solvent front.						
	27.7 cm.	27.2 cm. •	27.1 cm.	27.3 cm.	27.0 cm.	27.1 cm.	26.9 cm.
0 cm.	0.21	0.30	0.33	0.38	0.47	0.57	0.60
2	.23	.31	.35	.40	.47	.57	.58
4	.23	.30	.32	.38	.45	.56	.58
6	.23	.26	.30	.37	.43	.54	.55
8	.22	.24	.26	.36	.41	.52	.54
10	.20	.20	.22	.34	.39	.51	.52
12	.19	.16	.18	.30	.35	.48	.50
14	.17	.14	.15	.28	.33	.45	.48
16	.16	.13	.16	.27	.31	.42	.45
18	.15	.12	.14	.26	.30	.41	.43
20	.13	.11	.12	.20	.25	.37	.41
22	.11	.08	.12	.20	.23	.34	.38
24	.12	.07	.11	.13	.20	.32	.34
26	.13	.04	.05	.13	.14	.26	.25

DISCUSSION

The results recorded in Tables I—III clearly indicate that the rates of movement of the amino-acids depend to a considerable extent on the distance between the starting point and the source of solvent. In the descending as well as in the ascending methods of chromatography, the R_f values gradually decrease with the increase of this distance. The decrease at first is small, but as the distance considerably increases, there is a sharp fall in the R_f values. In the case of amino-acids with lower R_f values, no movement of the amino-acids could be observed when applied at large distances from the source of solvent. In the case of volatile solvents, such as *iso*propyl alcohol, pyridine and amyl alcohol, the extent of variation of R_f values with the distance from the source of solvent is greater than that in the case of less volatile solvents, such as phenol.

At short distances from the source of solvent, the R_f values are found to remain practically the same. In the case of ascending chromatography, the solution is usually applied close to the source of solvent (1.5 cm. to 2.5 cm. away), so that the results are less prone to variation. In the case of descending chromatography on the other hand, this distance is considerable (7 cm. to 10 cm.) and is thereby expected to count upon the final results. So care should be taken to maintain a constant distance of the starting point from the source of solvent to obtain reproducible results.

A decrease in R_f value with increasing distances is expected from the partition mechanism suggested for paper chromatography (Consden *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The composition of the mobile phase depends upon the amount of water taken up by cellulose of the filter paper for its saturation. As the developing solvent ascends or descends along the filter paper, more and more water is adsorbed by cellulose and thereby the mobile phase will be gradually depleted of its water-content. The water-content of the mobile phase thus depends on the distance from the source of solvent. The greater the distance from the source of solvent, the less will be the water-content of the mobile phase. Finally, the mobile phase may be completely robbed of its entire water-content as it appears from absence of any movement in certain cases at considerable distances.

Again, the smaller the amount of water in the mobile phase, the less will be the solubility of the amino-acid in that phase. Assuming the solubility in water-saturated cellulose to remain constant, the partition coefficient of the amino-acid (α) will increase with the decrease in solubility in the mobile phase. From the formula relating ' α ' and ' R_f ' (Consden *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) it is expected that with the increase in α , the value of R_f will decrease; this is practically found to be so.

A simple calculation will roughly show how much water the mobile phase loses after traversing a particular length of the filter paper. It may be roughly taken that at 25° the ratio of phenol and water in phenol saturated with water is 7 : 3, *i.e.*, percentage of water is 30. A strip of Whatman No. 1 filter paper of area 59. × 35 sq. cm. and of weight 1.7828 g. increases in weight by 3.7246 g. on development with phenol saturated with water. This is thereby equal to the total amount of phenol and water on the paper. If it is assumed that the filter paper adsorbs 20% water (International Critical Tables) the composition of the mobile phase roughly comes out to be 17 : 3, *i.e.*, percentage of water is 15. Thus, it is observed that the percentage of water in the mobile phase is about half of that in the original developing solvent. This, however, represents an average composition of the mobile phase; the exact composition is likely to vary throughout the strip. With a strip of greater length (70 cm.) the composition of the mobile phase is found to be still less (about 10% water) which clearly demonstrates the gradual loss of water by the mobile phase as it moves along the paper.

In the case of amino-acids of low R_f values, the rate of movement considerably slows down at greater distances. This is due to the fact that normally such amino-acids travel short distances and thereby experience less variation in the composition of the phase. When these amino-acids are applied at greater distances, the mobile phase coming in contact for the first time has a different composition from the initial. Amino-acids of high R_f values even normally pass through various phase-compositions and thereby are less affected when applied at greater distances.

In the case of pyridine-amyl alcohol-water (Table II), the R_f values are reduced to zero towards the end. Since with the pure solvents constituting this mixture no movement of the amino-acids is observed due to their insolubility or sparing solubility, it can be reasonably concluded that this solvent mixture after traversing a long distance is deprived of its water-content. That it can so happen was observed by Burstall *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 516) in the case of butyl alcohol saturated with water.

In the case of isopropyl alcohol-water (7 : 3) we can have a rough idea about the extent of decrease in water-content of the mobile phase from the R_f values of the amino-acids obtained with the mixture having various compositions (Burma and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). If we consider the R_f values of the amino-acids, when the latter are applied somewhere midway between the usual initial and final spots (say, 12 cm. away from the usual place near the edge), they are found to roughly correspond to those obtained when amino-acids are applied at the usual distance, but developed with isopropyl alcohol-water having the composition (75 : 25). If it is assumed that the R_f values usually measured represent the average of the values for different distances, it can be roughly speculated that the moving solvent loses about 5% water during its passage through half the distance of the chromatogram. While traversing the whole distance of it the decrease in R_f values in all cases is not found to be uniform for reasons already pointed out. Anyway, in this case the R_f values correspond on the average to the composition 25 : 15, *i.e.*, the total loss of water in traversing the entire distance is 15%.

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